

Effect of anthropogenicity on the composition and diversity of aquatic insects of a municipal river in North Central Nigeria

Augustine O. Edegbene^{1,2*}, Francis O. Arimoro², Obinnah Odoh² and Efe Ogidiaka³

¹Department of Biological Sciences (Applied Hydrobiology and Fisheries Unit), Sule Lamido University, PMB 048, Kafin Hausa, Nigeria

²Department of Biological Sciences (Applied Hydrobiology and Fisheries Unit), Federal University of Technology, PMB 65, Minna, Nigeria

³Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Delta State University, PMB 1, Abraka, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Composition and diversity of aquatic insects as influenced by anthropogenic activities in River Chanchaga, Niger State, Nigeria was investigated for a period of six months spanning from April through September, 2014 in three stations. Habitat and water quality were done using qualitative habitat evaluation index (QHEI) and America public health association (APHA) method of water analysis respectively. Aquatic insects were sampled with a kick net of about 250 μ m mesh size. QHEI values in the three stations showed that the stations were moderately impaired with station 1 having the highest value (64.3%), while canopy cover of the three sampled stations were relatively poor. Physicochemical parameters values were within the maximum permissible limit of water quality variables by Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA), Nigeria and Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON) except dissolved oxygen and pH. A total of 6 orders, 16 families, 19 taxa and 101 individuals of aquatic insects were recorded during the study. The overall abundance, distribution and composition of aquatic insects were poor. Station 1 had the highest number of species composition (55) while station 3 had only 6 individuals of aquatic insects. Simpson dominance (D) and Shannon-weiner index were highest in station 1. Station 3 was more even in aquatic insect distribution (0.8965) while station 1 had the highest margalef richness index (d) of 4.969. The pollution sensitive species in the group of Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Trichoptera (EPT) were poorly represented or even absent in some case probably owing to the deteriorating state of the sampled stations as a result of various human activities. Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) showed a very weak relationship between the insects' abundance and distribution and environmental variables measured. *Coelhydrus* sp., Chlorostidae, *Chironomus* sp., *Philodytes* sp., Cordulidae and *Neoperla* sp. were strongly associated with axis 1 and this association was explained by dissolved oxygen, phosphate and water depth. Bray-curtis similarity index performed revealed that samples were more clustered by months than by stations. The research was able to provide a baseline study as a biomonitoring tool for the assessment of the integrity of water bodies in Niger State and Nigeria in general.

Citation: Edegbene AO, Arimoro FO, Odoh O and Ogidiaka E (2015). Effect of anthropogenicity on the composition and diversity of aquatic insects of a municipal river in North Central Nigeria. *Biosciences Research in Today's World* 1: 55-66.

Received May 31, 2015; **Accepted** July 2, 2015; **Published** July 19, 2015.

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Competing Interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

* **E-mail:** ovieedes@gmail.com

This research work was presented at the Biosciences Research Support Foundation (BRSF)'s 1st International Conference on Biosciences Research (ICBR), Awka, Nigeria, 25-27 May 2015.

Keywords: anthropogenic activities; aquatic insect diversity; biomonitoring; ecological state; EPT; Chanchaga River; Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Lately, there have been increasing studies on freshwater bodies globally and Nigeria in particular and the effect of anthropogenic activities on the diversity and distribution of aquatic macroinvertebrates [1,2,3]. Several biota have been used in assessing the integrity of water course in Europe, North America, Africa and other continents [4]. Among this biota are macrobenthic invertebrates, in which the aquatic insects belong. Their use as biomonitoring tool is mainly as a result of their diversity, life cycle, sedentary nature and convenient size for field examination [5].

Aquatic ecosystem is been used as source of drinking water, discharge of untreated wastes, irrigation, washing of households, generation of hydropower on the river catchments [6]. Major source of pollution in Nigeria inland water ways is industrial effluents and untreated municipal discharges. These activities may have deleterious effect on the ecological alteration of the water system and the inhabitant biota [7, 2]. Most inland water in Nigeria particularly those in urban and semi urban areas are now being used as source of discharging both liquid and solid wastes. These activities have high degree of debilitating effect on the sustainability and functionality on the aquatic resource and River Chanchaga is not let off.

River Chanchaga, is an important river flowing through several Local Government Areas in Niger State of Nigeria. It is a municipal river which is mainly used by the riparian communities and environs as source of potable water, irrigation and other domestic activities. Some reaches of the river is presently faced with perturbation arising from car washing, bathing, illegal gold mining, industrial activities at its catchment.

The composition, distribution and diversity of aquatic insects in a river system can be influenced by anthropogenic activities [2, 8]. In the face of increasing human activity in catchments of this said river, there is need to assess the present status of the habitat and water quality and the benthic aquatic insects assemblage and diversity as tool for biomonitoring in future planning.

Studies of this kind in developed countries have been well established using different indices and drivers of change, but in developing countries like Nigeria, where there are existing laws guiding the water ways but are not been enforced, probably as a result of socio-economic developments. This present study serves as baseline information on the biomonitoring of the River Chanchaga that can be used by river managers for planning and improving development around the studied river course. In line with this assertion, the objective of this study was to assess the effect of human activities on the composition, distribution and

diversity of aquatic insects of River Chanchaga, Niger State, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 The study area

River Chanchaga a 5th (5^o) order river is a located in southern part of Niger State. The River is about 215.61km in length, it takes its source from Mutundaya in Shiroro Local Government Area and flows southward through Zhabyala, Zhalape, Shakwata, Shakwatu, Numbupi, Bali, Shaukikafuta, Shagna, Tunga Waya, Kadna, Chanchaga, Korokpan, Kakaki, Shiri, Tadagona, Manmagi, Tswadan, Emiworogi, Twata Dinkoso, Kenchi, Tsantsaga, Badeggi, Emijiko, Tswatagi, Shidisaba, Ndakwudu, Ekwuti and terminates at Gedede where it joins River Niger. It lies between the interception of latitudes 8°43'N to 9°40'N and longitudes 6°12'E to 6°47'E of the equator. It is a municipal river with many tributaries including River Guduko, River Gorax, River Gbako and Tagwai dam. There are many anthropogenic activities going on in the river, which include illegal gold mining, sand dredging, bathing, washing, farming, irrigation activities, indiscriminate defaecation, fishing, etc. Fishing in the area is dominated by artisanal fishermen that use manually operated wooden (dug out) canoes. River Chanchaga is used by the Niger State Water Board, as the main distribution channel of water to Minna, the State capital and its environs. The area is a tropical climate with mean annual temperature of 30.2°C, relative humidity of 61% and annual rainfall ranged between 1200 mm and 1300 mm. The vegetative cover reflects that of guinea savanna zone, characterized by sparsely distributed trees species, shrubs and dominated by grassland. The area shows two distinct seasons i.e. a rainy and dry season. The rainy season is between April to October with a peak rainfall occurring in September and dry season is between November to March.

For the purpose of this study, three (3) well marked stations were selected based on accessibility and level of anthropogenic activities. The three stations are; Tunga Waya, Chanchaga (Water Board) and Korokpan Communities (Fig. 1).

2.1.2 Sampling stations

2.1.3 Station 1

Tunga Waya community (Latitude 9°35 'N and longitude 6°39'E) in Bosso Local Government Area is the station 1. It is about 19.71 km from river source. The rural dwellers are mostly farmers. They cultivate yam, maize, melon, okra and cowpea. Apart from the farming activities going on around the riparian zone of the station, other activities like cattle grazing, bathing, washing and irrigation process is still carried out here. The riparian vegetations are mixed

probably because of the degree of anthropogenicity. The canopy cover is sparse with more of shrubs and grass which make the station to be open most part of the year most especially during the dry season. The station microhabitat is dominated by pool, the riffle and run microhabitats are sparse. Due to the level of perturbation, the station is prone to erosional process. The station bottom consist more of mud and hardpan (clay). Sand, silt and cobbles biotopes are less.

2.1.4 Station 2

Station 2 is located in Chanchaga (Water Board) (Latitude 9°32'N and longitude 6°34'E) in Chanchaga Local Government Area. This station is about 4.23km from station 1. The riparian vegetations are mostly mixed. The station is immediately after the crest of the water board, it is highly perturbed due the presence of water board, block industries, mining activities, farming, indiscriminate defaecation and a leprosy centre upstream of the station. The stream bed is more of boulders, then sand and mud. The station is relatively straight with little or no meanders. Mango tree (*Mangifera indica*) form a little canopy cover in the site, but most part of the station is open surrounded by farm land. The dominant riparian vegetation there is *Nuclea latifolia* (Rubiaceae).

2.1.4 Station 3

Korokpan community (Latitude 9°31'N and longitude 6°32'E), station 3 is also located in Chanchaga Local Government Area. This station is about 1.49 km from station 2. The riparian zone harbours residential structure, thus leading to the absence of native vegetation. Agricultural activities are very high. Local mining activities, sand dredging, bathing, defaecation, washing of cars, clothes and other households are among the numerous anthropogenic activities going on around the bank of this station. The streambed consists of sand, boulders, mud; stump of wood and decay organic particles. The decay organic matters are mainly at the littoral zone of the station. The instream cover is relatively poor, rendering the water body open.

2.1.5 Habitat quality survey

The qualitative habitat evaluation index (QHEI) is a physical habitat index designed to provide an empirical, quantitative evaluation of the general lotic microhabitat characteristics that are important to aquatic communities [9]. The QHEI is composed of six principal metrics i.e. substrate, instream cover, channel morphology, riparian zone, pool quality, riffle quality and gradient [9], with maximum possible QHEI site score of 100. Each of the metrics was scored individually and then summed to provide the total QHEI, site score. At each sampling station a reach of 25m was selected and habitat characterization was carried out. A description

of the stream, summary of aquatic plants, measurements of instream parameters such as depth, width, and flow velocity and streambed type were included.

2.1.6 Water sampling

Water samples were collected monthly over a period of 6 months between April and September 2014 at each station. On site, during each sampling event, subsurface water temperatures, dissolved oxygen conductivity, pH, water depth and flow velocity were measured. A mercury-in-glass thermometer was used for measuring temperature. A HANNA HI 9828 multi-probe metre manufactured by HANNA instruments was used for measuring values of DO, Conductivity and pH. Average mid-channel water velocity was measured in three replicates by timing a float as it moved over a distance of 10 m [10]. Water depth was measured in the sample area using a calibrated rod. Transparency was measured using secchi disc. Water samples were collected in 1-l plastic acid washed bottles and transported to the laboratory in a cooler box containing ice. In the laboratory, water samples were analysed for BOD₅, sulphate and phosphate according to [11] methods. Analysis of all samples commenced within 24 h of sampling. Substratum composition in each 25- m sampling reach was estimated visually as percentage of silt, sand, stone and clay [12].

2.1.7 Aquatic insect sampling

At each sampling station a four 3-min samples were taken on each sampling visit to include all different substrate and flow regime zones. Kick samples of aquatic insects were collected monthly (April, 2014 – September, 2014) with D-frame net (250µm mesh size) within an approximately 25m wadeable portion of the river. Samples collected from the net were preserved in 70% ethanol and transferred to the laboratory for sorting and identification. At the laboratory samples were washed in a 250µm mesh sieve to remove sand and aquatic insects were then picked from the substrate with aid of a forceps and microscope. Sorted aquatic insect were identified to the lowest taxonomic level possible, mostly genus, according to [13, 14, 15]. Reference was also made to the taxonomic lists of species known to be present in Nigeria [e.g. 16, 17].

2.1.8 Data analyses

The range, mean and standard deviation for each physical and chemical variable was calculated per station. Summary of biological metrics including abundance, number of taxa, Shannon diversity index, evenness, Simpson dominance, Margalef's index as well as physical and chemical variables were compared between stations using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significant differences between stations indicated by ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) were

Figure 1: Map of the Study area showing the study stations

followed by Tukey's post hoc HSD test. Taxa richness (Margalef's index), Simpson dominance diversity (Shannon index) and evenness indices were calculated using the computer BASIC program SP DIVERS [18]. Cluster analysis based on Bray-Curtis similarity index was used to ascertain whether aquatic insects assemblage distribution was influenced mostly either by differences in sampling stations or months. Cluster analysis was performed on $\log(x+1)$ transformed macroinvertebrate abundance data. Cluster analysis were performed using PAST statistical package [19]. Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) was used to evaluate relationships between aquatic insects composition, distribution and environmental variables using PAST statistical package [19]. Prior to the final CCA, variables exhibiting high multi-collinearity (Pearson

correlation $r > 0.80$, $p < 0.05$) were removed. Rare species, occurring less than 1 % of sampling event at each sampling station, were not included in the CCA. Physical and chemical variables used for the CCA analysis were also $\log(x+1)$ transformed to prevent the undue influences of extreme values on the final CCA ordination. Species-environment correlation coefficients provided a measure of the explanation of community patterns by individual physical and chemical variables. A Monte Carlo permutation test with 199 permutations [20] was used to assess the significance of the first three canonical axes. % Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Trichoptera (EPT) and % Chironomids were calculated by dividing the number of EPT and Chironomids recorded by the total abundance of aquatic insects in each study station [21].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Environmental variables: habitat and water quality

Canopy cover of the riparian zone in the three sampled stations were 48%, 25% and 12% for stations 2, 1 and 3 respectively in decreasing order (Fig. 2). Qualitative Habitat Evaluation Index (QHEI) using the habitat quality characterization showed that station 1 had a QHEI of 64.3%, followed by station 2 (59.62%), while station 3 was had relatively low QHEI value (42.69%) (Fig. 3).

The mean and standard deviation of the physical and chemical variables in each sampling station are shown in Table 1 below. Station mean of all the physical and chemical variables showed significant difference.

Water temperature, transparency, flow velocity, conductivity and phosphate were statistically significant among the stations and months sampled ($p < 0.05$), while water depth, pH and DO showed no significant difference among the months sampled ($p > 0.05$) but statistically significant among the stations ($p > 0.05$). DO was highly significant in the months sampled ($p = 0.000135$). Sulphate was statistically not significant among the months and stations ($p > 0.05$). The value of the variables were within the range of the maximum permissible limit for water quality variables by Federal Environmental Agency, Nigeria (FEPA) and the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) except dissolved oxygen (DO) and pH (Table 1).

The canopy cover of the three sampled stations were relatively poor, probably due to the geographical location of the river which is guinea savannah, usually characterized by sparse trees and grass. This is in contrast with earlier report by [22, 23] who recorded relatively high canopy cover range of 25 – 72% in River Orogo in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria. The reason for this variance may be due to difference in their habitat type and geographical region.

The qualitative habitat evaluation index (QHEI) also showed that the three stations were impaired. According to [24], QHEI score less than 21% showed a habitat is severely impaired while QHEI score between 29% and 79% are moderately impaired. QHEI greater than 79% are not impaired. Judging from this proposition, it showed that the three stations of the River Chanchaga are moderately impaired with station 1 having a promising habitat type when compared to stations 2 and 3 with varied degree degradation. This result is in line with earlier report elsewhere in Ethiopia at Kebena and Akaki Rivers in Addis Ababa [25] whose QHEI range between 30.6 – 59.0% in all the sixteen (16) stations they sampled. Contrarily, [26] reported a contrary result in a study conducted in Owan River, Southern Nigeria, where QHEI value range of 54.6 – 79.6% was recorded. This QHEI value recorded in this present study may be due to the high degree of anthropogenic

activities carried out in the various reaches of the River Chanchaga, thus leading to the debilitating effect on the habitat and the aquatic resources.

The physicochemistry of water bodies and their immediate biotopes are significant factor determining the distribution, abundance and diversity of aquatic biota [27, 2]. Any activity which will inhibit the quality of water will lead to rapid deterioration of habitat which will in turn affect the wellbeing of the aquatic communities [28, 29]. The chemistry of the water of an aquatic environment can be determined by disturbance from the local surroundings, land use patterns and other human activities in their various reaches of the water body [30]. In view of this to sustain and protect the aquatic resources, it is important to know the factor having negative impact on the resources and proffer management measures [31]. River Chanchaga is an important municipal water body serving the immediate riparian communities source for varied domestic activities and the Niger State water board authority also use the river as its distribution source to Minna, the State capital and environs. Due to this large human impact, the river has been subjected to high degree of deterioration in its catchments and the aquatic resource. The low DO (0.93 – 3.50 mg/l) and the high nutrients recorded during the study are indicators of anthropogenic activities. The influx of washing detergents, run-offs from surrounding farm lands and the presence of illegal gold mining points in some reaches of the river are likely responsible for the perceived deterioration of the water and habitat quality. Station 3 with the highest nutrients value and lowest DO value is indicative of increased organic pollution occurring in this station when compared to stations 1 and 2. Again the on site and point source activities of the illegal gold miners in station 3 lend more credence to the appalling state of the surface water quality. The effect of human activities like cassava peel soaking, saw mill waste discharge, washing and other human activities have been reported by various authors to have a debilitating effect on aquatic biota [32,28,34,34,35]. The relatively high conductivity value also shows human disturbance. The value range of conductivity recorded in this present study is slightly in consonant with the value recorded by [29] in a creek in Niger Delta area of Nigeria. In a similar study by [35] in Wushishi dam in Niger State, Nigeria also shows relatedness in conductivity value. Generally, the slight increase in the conductivity of this study is also a fact to note, on the disturbing nature of the river system. The pH of this present study varied from slightly acidic to highly alkaline. Station 3 had a pH of 12.0, this may be attributed to the dominant boulders and rocks biotopes in this station coupled with the degree of anthropogenic influence by the illegal gold miners. Also, the closeness of water board may also increase the alkalinity of the water, probably due to the chemicals used by the water board for purification of water before distribution

Fig. 2. % Canopy cover of the sampled stations of River Chanchaga, Niger State North Central Nigeria

Fig. 3. Qualitative habitat evaluation index (%) of the sampled stations of River Chanchaga, Niger State North Central Nigeria

to the appropriate channels.

The surface water temperature in this study area are relatively high when compared with results recorded by [28, 29] in southern Nigeria. The increased temperature most especially at station 3 may be as a result of sparse canopy cover and absence of aquatic macrophytes in the station. Station 3 transparency value was much more lower than that of other stations. This further lend credence to the state of perturbation of the said station largely due to human influences [35].

3.2 Composition, distribution and abundance of aquatic insects

A total of six (6) orders of aquatic insects represented by 16 families and 19 taxa were

recorded in the water body (Table 2). 101 individuals benthic aquatic insects abundance was encountered during the course of this study with station 1 having 55, station 2 (40) and station 3 (6). Ephemeroptera and plecoptera were represented in stations 1 and 2. Overall, abundance, distribution and composition of aquatic insects in the river course was sparse except *Pseudocloeon* sp., Oligoneuridae and *Coelhydrus* sp. which were represented by 10, 20 and 9 individuals respectively (Table 2). A total of 101 individual aquatic insects and 19 species were recorded in River Chanchaga during the study period. This number is relatively low when compared to the total aquatic insect species recorded in some relatively unperturbed rivers in southern Nigeria [21, 2]. The relatively low composition, distribution and abundance of aquatic insects recorded in this study could be

Table 1. Summary of physicochemical parameters of the study stations of Chanchaga River, (April 2014- September 2014), Niger State, North Central Nigeria

Parameters	St1	St2	St3	Month		Station		FEPA Max. permissible limit	SON Max. permissible limit
				F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value		
Water temperature (°C)	27.83± 1.44 ^a (25.5-29.5)	28.33 ±2.09 ^b (26.0-31.5)	28.08± 1.96 ^c (27.0-32.0)	3.29	0.051	0.19	0.83		
Water depth (m)	0.33± 0.21 ^a (0.1 -0.66)	0.31± 0.19 ^b (0.12-0.57)	0.42± 0.23 ^c (0.18-0.84)	6.66	0.0056	1.28	0.321		
Transparency (cm)	7.5 ±7.73 ^a (2.0-23)	0.82± 9.51 ^b (3.5-24.5)	7.50 ±6.15 ^c (3.5-18.23)	2.69	0.086	0.48	0.63		
Flow velocity (m/s)	0.27± 0.17 ^a (0.06-0.46)	0.40 ±0.55 ^b (0.08-1.49)	0.21± 0.14 ^c (0.02-0.38)	2.25	0.13	0.67	0.53		
Conductivity (µscm ⁻¹)	10.4 ±1.82 ^a (8.6-12.8)	9.97 ±2.03 ^b (8.5-14.0)	16.28 ±1.47 ^c (8.5-12.0)	0.84	0.55	0.09	0.91	-	1000
pH	7.43 (6.0-10)	7.55 (6.9-9.0)	7.90 (6.9-12.0)	10.87	0.00086	0.70	0.52	6.0 – 9.0	6.5 – 8.5
DO (mg/l)	2.67 ±0.57 ^a (1.88-3.5)	2.38 ±0.73 ^b (1.25-3.40)	2.095± 0.68 ^c (0.93-2.56)	16.92	-0.000135	7.1188	0.1195	5.0	-
BOD ₅ (mg/l)	1.311 ±0.33 ^a (0.93-1.72)	1.157± 0.213 ^b (0.821-1.38)	0.543 ±0.282 ^c (-0.03-0.69)	1.0155	0.457	12.7508	0.00177	10.0	-
Sulphate (mg/l)	22.318 ±3.948 ^a (18.06-28.0)	27.073 ±0.0459 ^b (16.41-32.64)	23.63± 3.964 ^c (21-26.56)	6.174	0.0073	4.3593	0.0435	200 -400	100
Phosphate (mg/l)	1.502± 0.831 ^a (0.52-2.49)	1.393 ± 0.672 ^b (0.47-2.46)	1.3983 ±0.6075 ^c (0.56-8.39)	2.8622	0.0738	0.0721	0.9309	20	50

Note: Values are means ± standard deviation, minimum and maximum values in parenthesis. The F-value indicates ANOVA and p-value indicates the level probability. Stations means with same superscript value indicate no significance difference.

Table 2. Composition, distribution and abundance of aquatic insects in River Chanchaga, North Central Nigeria (April-September 2014).

Order	Family	Taxon	Code	Station		
				1	2	3
Odonata	Gomphidae	<i>Ictinogomphus</i> sp.	Ict	7	1	2
	Aeschnidae	<i>Aeschna</i> sp.	Aes	2	1	0
	Calopterygidae		Cal	2	0	0
	Libellulidae	<i>Urothermis</i> sp.	Uro	1	0	1
	Chlorostidae		Chl	1	0	0
	Coenagrionidae	<i>Coenagrion</i> sp.	Coe	1	1	0
	Cordulidae		Cor	2	0	0
Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Pseudocloeon</i> sp.	Pse	10	4	0
		<i>Bugilliesia</i> sp.	Bug	4	2	1
	Caenidae	<i>Caenis</i> sp.	Cae	1	0	0
	Oligoneuridae		Oli	4	20	0
	Hepatgeniidae	<i>Afronurus</i> sp.	Afr	1	2	0
Plecoptera	Perlidae	<i>Neoperla</i> sp.	Neo	1	5	0
Hemiptera	Belostomatidae	<i>Appasus</i> sp.	App	5	2	0
Coleoptera	Dytiscidae	<i>Cybister</i> sp.	Cyb	2	1	0
		<i>Coelhydrus</i> sp.	Col	9	1	0
		<i>Philodytes</i> sp.	Phi	2	0	0
Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Chironomus</i> sp.	Chi	1	0	0
	Psychodidae		Psy	0	0	1
Total				55	40	6

Table 3. Diversity and dominance of aquatic insect in the study stations of River Chanchaga, April-September 2014, Niger State, North Central Nigeria

	Stations		
	1	2	3
Number of taxa	21	11	4
Individuals	56	40	7
Simpson 1 –D	0.9075	0.7137	0.6939
Shannon-weiner index (H)	2.679	1.747	1.277
Evenness index (E)	0.6939	0.5217	0.8965
Margalef index (d)	4.969	2.711	1.542
%EPT	38.2	70.0	16.7
% Chironomids	1.9	0.0	0.0

attributed to high degree of anthropogenic activities, poor habitat type and absence of aquatic macrophytes which serves as microhabitat to species of macroinvertebrates. Diversity and abundance of aquatic macroinvertebrates have been used to determine the ecological status of water bodies globally and in Africa [2,36,37,38,31].

The Odonata of the aquatic insects recorded in this station is the most diverse group with each species having representative in most of the stations sampled. Odonates was well represented in station 1 compared to stations 2 and 3. The favourable physicochemistry conditions, increased habitat quality and canopy cover were probable factors accounting for the increased species richness and diversity in this station. Also, the odonata generally prefer

aquatic vegetation as refuge and again the high canopy cover of this station may also lend credence to the diversity of odonates in station 1 [17,31].

Ephemeroptera immediately followed odonata in diversity and distribution, but was the most ubiquitous aquatic insects in the study stations except station 1 were only *Bugilliesia* sp. was represented by one individual. Other researchers have also reported ephemeroptera abundance in various researches conducted in southern Nigeria [39, 23, 2]. The family baetidae was the most represented in the study area, similar to report by [2]. Some species of baetidae have been reported to be associated with high flow velocity [21]. In a broad view, the ephemeroptera group are well low in diversity when compared with other research conducted in other parts of Nigeria [39, 37, 23].

Fig. 4. Triplot of the first and second CCA axes of aquatic insect taxa, environmental variables and the sampling stations. Aquatic insect abbreviation: Ict (*Ictinogomphus* sp.), Aes (*Aeschna* sp.), Cal (Calopterygidae), Uro (*Urothermis* sp.), Chl (Chlorostidae), Coe (*Coenagrion* sp.), Cor (Cordulidae), Pse (*Pseudocloeon* sp.), Bug (*Bugilliesia* sp.), Cae (*Caenis* sp.), Oli (Oligoneuridae), Afr (*Afronurus* sp.), Neo (*Neoperla* sp.), App (*Appasus* sp.), Cyb (*Cybister* sp.), Col (*Coelhydrus* sp.), Phi (*Philodytes* sp.), Chi (*Chironomus* sp.), Psy (Psychodidae).

Fig. 5. Dendrogram derived from the cluster analysis (Bray-Curtis similarity index) of log (x+1) transformed aquatic insect abundance data in the River Chanchaga during the study periods (April–September 2014). Apr April, May May, Jun June, Jul July, Aug August, Sep September. Numbers 1, 2 and 3 attached to the months represent the sampling stations.

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Ephemeroptera immediately followed Odonata in diversity and distribution, but was the most ubiquitous aquatic insects in the study stations except station 1 where only *Bugilliesia* sp. was represented by one individual. Other researchers have also reported Ephemeroptera abundance in various researches conducted in southern Nigeria [39,23,2]. The family Baetidae was the most represented in the study area, similar to report by [2]. Some species of Baetidae have been reported to be associated with high flow velocity [21]. In a broad view, the Ephemeroptera group are well low in diversity when compared with other research conducted in other parts of Nigeria [39,37,23]. The high abundance of this group in their studies was attributed to their sensitivity to pollution load, so this shows that the sampled stations of this study area have been subjected to pollution loads. The Caenidae only represented by *Caenis* sp. with 1 individual in station 1 had earlier been reported to be tolerant of aquatic pollution [40]. However, in this present study it was relatively low in distribution which shows a contrary view to the earlier report because from the habitat and water quality and even the wholistic distribution and abundance of aquatic insects in this study have showed that the river is perturbed. Oligoneuridae which had the highest number of individuals during this study shows its tolerance level to perturbation, this revealed that it can be used as bioindicator of water quality.

Plecoptera (stone fly) was only represented by one species *Neoperla* sp. and with 1 and 5 individuals in stations 1 and 2 respectively and absent in station 3. This lend more credence to the perturbed nature of station 3. It has earlier been reported that the Plecoptera are very sensitive aquatic insect group [41]. Coleoptera was represented by one family and three taxa. The presence of some species of Dytiscidae have been reported to indicate pollution free water [42]. Judging from this, the low representation of Dytiscidae shows gross pollution effect on the water body.

Contrary to initial report that most species of Diptera are pollution tolerant in this present study, only 2 families of Diptera were recorded; Chironomidae represented by *Chironomus* sp. and Psychodidae which were in stations 1 and 3 respectively. In view of this, this group can be used as pollution sensitive species owing to the

fact that they were less represented and even absent in some stations of this study area.

3.3 Diversity, evenness, dominance, %EPT and %Chironomid

A summary of taxa, individuals, Simpson dominance, Shannon-weiner index (H), Evenness (E), Margalef index (d), %EPT and %Chironomid is shown in Table 3. Stations 1, 2 and 3 were represented by 19, 11 and 4 taxa respectively. Simpson dominance (D) was highest in station 1 but stations 2 and 3 showed no significant difference ($p>0.05$). Shannon-weiner index (H) was much lower in station 3 (1.277) but station 1 had the highest (2.67). Station 3 was even in aquatic insects distribution (0.8965), followed by station 1 and Margalef richness index (d) was relatively high in station 1 (4.969), but much lower in station 3 (1.542).

Ephemeroptera Plecoptera and Trichoptera (EPT) richness was highest in station 2 (70.0%), followed by station 1 (38.2%), but relatively low in station 3 (16.7%). Chironomids were not recorded in stations 2 and 3 and very low in station 1 (1.9%).

Diversity indices of aquatic insects performed for the study area show that most of the reaches of the river is highly polluted. The Margalef's index were less than 3 except that of station 1 which was 4.969. Margalef's water quality index value greater than 3 indicate clean water conditions [43]. This lend more evidence to the perturbed state of stations 2 and 3. The EPT richness was relatively low in station 3, further proving the point that the station has been subjected to high degree of anthropogenicity.

3.4 Relationship between some environmental variables and aquatic insects

Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) showed a very weak relationship between the species abundance and distribution of the aquatic insects and environmental parameters measured. Axes 1 and 2 of the canonical correspondence accounted for about 48% of the variation in the data set pooled during the study period. Monte Carlo permutation test showed that the first three canonical axes were not significant ($p>0.05$). *Coelhydrus* sp., Chlorostidae, *Chironomus* sp., *Philodytes* sp., Cordulidae and *Neoperla* sp. were strongly associated with axis 1 and these were explained by dissolved oxygen (DO), phosphate and water depth (Fig. 4). Most of the specimen sampled in stations 1 and 2 in August and September were positioned on the right while other months and station collection were positioned on the left except the samples collected in stations 1 and 3 in May and station 2 in April were positioned on the left close to the centre of the plot. *Ictinogomphus* sp. and *Pseudocloeon* sp. that were common in the study area were closely associated with April and May collection on the

centre point of the plot while Oligoneuridae and *Coelhydrus* sp. which were associated with station 2 in August on the right and station 1 in July on the left.

Coelhydrus sp., Chlorostidae and *Chironomus* sp. were negatively associated with dissolved oxygen, while *Philodytes* sp. and Cordulidae were associated positively with water depth and phosphate respectively. Oligoneuridae, *Afronurus* sp. and *Neoperla* sp. were outstanding aquatic insects having no relationship with any environmental variables. *Neoperla* sp. was only recorded in station 2 in September.

On the environmental variables, transparency, sulphate, conductivity, BOD₅, water temperature had no relationship with the aquatic insects. Dissolved oxygen was negatively correlated with transparency and pH while water temperature was positively correlated with BOD₅, conductivity, sulphate, phosphate and water depth.

The cluster analysis formed based on aquatic insects log(x+1) transformed abundance data revealed that samples were clustered by months mainly than by stations. Sample collected in May in station 2 and June in station 3 were more closely associated than other clusters (Fig. 5).

The CCA ordination showed that the aquatic insects were poorly associated with environmental factor measured in River Chanchaga. Phosphate, water depth were higher in September while flow velocity and water temperature were relatively high in July and August in station 3. Cordulidae was highly associated with increased phosphate lending credence to the fact that it can dwell in an organically polluted area, thus it is suggested that this species can be used as indicator species for aquatic ecosystem status. *Coelhydrus* sp., chlorostidae and *Chironomus* sp. were associated with reduced DO value. From the association of these organisms and DO, it can be inferred that these group of aquatic insects are pollution tolerant species. Several studies have reported most especially some group of chironomidae to be pollution tolerant species [21, 2].

This present study revealed that the increased human activities lead to the low abundance and diversity of aquatic insects in the sampled stations of River Chanchaga. The catchments of the river are used for various domestic activities such as farm lands, illegal gold mining points, industrial centres, etc., which is having a great negative effect on the aquatic biota.

4. CONCLUSION

Rivers in Niger State such as River Niger which River Chanchaga empty into which has earlier been reported to be rich in biodiversity, but

because of increasing human influence as a result of urbanization is now perturbed. This study have been able to outline the various causes of instability in the community structure of aquatic insects in River Chanchaga. Information from this report can serve as a baseline data set of macroinvertebrate fauna in the river. This can form a biomonitoring tool for assessing river integrity in Niger State and North central Nigeria in particular.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

AOE and FOA designed the study, performed the statistical analysis and wrote the draft of the manuscript. AOE and OO did the sample collection, identification and analysis while EO managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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